

**«THE PRINCIPLE OF DEMONSTRATION IN TEACHING
THE UZBEK LANGUAGE»**

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Annotation: In this article, the principle of demonstration in teaching the Uzbek language the methodological aspects of mother tongue and literature teaching are described, taking into account recent developments and developments in the field of teaching. In addition, methods of applying scientific and theoretical data in practice are described.

Keywords: Uzbek language, demonstration, method, technological system, education system, acceptable, system, philology, topic, object.

Fiction reflects the being through vivid scenes, images. By its very nature, literature is a visual representation of your being. However, other forms of art such as film, television, music, fine arts, as well as simple subjects in nature can help in literature classes. They serve as an additional source of information for literature lessons, allow the formation and development of aesthetic feelings in students, as well as help to more deeply imprint the images created by the author in the minds of students. At present, various cinemas, televisions, epidiascopes, tape recorders, and the like are available in every school. As a result, the range of visual aids has expanded. This is especially true if almost every school now has a computer connected to the Internet. In addition, mobile phones have a high capacity for photo, video and audio recording, which can be used wisely for display. Demonstration promotes conscious and active acquisition of knowledge. Musical works that are processed in the mind, consciously and correctly expressed in singing, are firmly rooted. Works that are understandable to students, that is, works that are appropriate to their age and individual characteristics and level of preparation, can be consciously mastered. Systematized knowledge is mastered more thoroughly. The robustness of learning depends on many factors: the scientific and systematic nature of teaching, the awareness of the students, the reason for learning, the quality of music textbooks, the skills of the music teacher. Proper organization of the activities of all the senses is very important for the reception and acquisition of knowledge. The more involved the senses, the easier it is to know. Demonstration is an important part of teaching literature. Because the nature of this science requires more demonstration. Understanding the essence of abstract concepts in language requires extensive use of this principle. The student acquires a clear understanding of events and their expressions through

language. The main task of the exhibition in literature classes is to help students to understand the literary work, to help them to fully imagine the work of the writer, to create additional opportunities for the acquisition of literary-theoretical concepts, to ensure the development of students' speech. In other words, it is to help the literature teacher solve all the tasks that lie ahead. The tasks of the exhibition can be very diverse. There are many types of exhibitions today: illustrative and graphic, drawing, materials, gramophone recordings and radio broadcasts, film fragments and educational films, telefragment and television lessons. Each of these can be visual, auditory, or synthetic. Demonstration methods are forms of learning that are largely dependent on the visual aids and techniques used in the learning process. In other words, the visual aids of education determine the nature of the study and acquisition of literary knowledge. When using such teaching methods, students' knowledge of literature depends on the emotional images and imaginations that are formed or reminded by visual aids. Verbal explanation helps to organize observation, to harmonize ideas, to connect them with the idea of the subject of the studied literature. Without visual aids, verbal explanation would be of little use. As a visual aid, posters and slides can be displayed in the Uzbek language class. Demonstrations using a variety of technology: film and other projection equipment, sound recorders, etc. are now widespread in the educational process. Demonstration weapons have different meanings. They are only displayed in one case. In the second case, it facilitates the process of abstraction formation. Relying on clear emotional images created with the help of visual aids facilitates the process of mastering abstract rules, increases the level of comprehensibility of knowledge. For example, etc. They are used. Visual aids, in particular, help to systematize and enrich knowledge gained from literature, as well as to activate students' thinking activities. It is difficult to imagine a literature teacher using a visual aid in the teaching process without a verbal statement or comment. The visual medium is always in touch with the teacher's word and in a certain way. The importance of applying the principle of demonstration in the learning process can be explained in terms of the theory, which gives a great place to the emotional perception of the subject, their live observation, the unity of explicit and abstract, emotional, logical and theoretical elements in cognitive activity. Literature lessons have great potential for visual comprehension. It is not the visuals themselves that are remembered, but their combination with speech and action is most effective. This indicates the need to look for the optimal combination of teaching methods. Based on this, it is

necessary to plan the individual way of cognition in the teaching process as a real unit of emotional and theoretical cognition. In order for the use of visual teaching methods in a literature class to meet the criteria of optimality, a literature teacher must follow a number of requirements when selecting them. The choice of demonstration methods should take into account the fact that they are more successful in solving the following didactic tasks:

- help students to develop visual thinking in the understanding of concepts;
- to play the role of a means of activating attention in the development of activities;
- to be able to concretize the knowledge received from the literature;
- clarify and classify the studied topics in posters, graphics, pictures, etc.;
- play the role of methods of stimulating interest in the language, creating guidelines for effective learning;
- allows to receive information in a concrete form on the level of mastery of the study material in the field of literature.

The use of visual aids in literature lessons ensures the effectiveness of the lesson. To do this, the teacher is able to communicate the topic to a wide range of students using a variety of methods, based on their tireless creative work and experience. It is no secret that science and technology are developing rapidly today. Therefore, it is possible to organize lessons on the life and works of literature in schools with the help of modern technologies and to analyze students' impressions of the current situation in a comparative way during the lesson, which allows them to directly form and express students' worldviews. The use of photo albums that relate to the creators in the classroom, as well as the artist's artistry in the painting, directly increases the student's interest in the material available and prepares the ground for serious reflection. An important task for the teacher is to ensure that students understand and learn about the author's work and his works of art, literary and theoretical knowledge, and to develop his literary discourse through the purposeful use of visual aids in literature lessons. Students need to be more active in demonstration classes. If they do not have this activity, for example, in the classes on the centuries of fine arts, the activity of students is not noticeable. It doesn't matter what the show is. One of the leading trends in the socio-economic development of developed countries is the process of informatization of all spheres of human activity, as well as education. Nowadays, teachers have at their disposal a variety of visual aids, such as art and graphics, radio broadcasts and recordings, film clips, educational and film films, TV clips, slides, and more. They include screen, audio,

and synthetic visuals. As An Amos Comenius put it, "Everything that is possible must be conveyed in order to be felt." Another great educator, KDUshinsky, writes: "An educator who wants something to be imprinted in a child's memory has as many senses as possible: eyes, ears, sound, sense of muscle movements, and even, if possible, smell and it should also be concerned that it contributes to the memory of taste." According to the principle of demonstration, the study of linguistic phenomena begins with observation, perception. The child perceives through different sounds, words, sentences, pronunciation, hearing, writing and seeing. Through observation, children develop an emotionally clear picture of language phenomena. The teacher leads the children from the perception of linguistic phenomena to their understanding, from the perception of linguistic phenomena to the comprehensive mastery of grammatical concepts. Visual aids are also an important source of information. Because the student can get the same information from textbooks, teacher's statements, newspapers and magazines, as well as from visual aids.

References and sources used:

1. Methods of teaching literature [Mant] / textbook: K. Husanboyeva, R. Niyaz Metova.: "Barkamol fayz media" publishing house, 2018.
2. Y. Gulomov, Inomjon Rasulov, Hasan Rustamov, Belgi Mirzaakhmedov. Methods of teaching the Uzbek language, Tashkent, "Teacher", 1995.
3. Askar Gulomov. Principles and methods of teaching the native language. "Tashkent", "Teacher", 1992.
4. Improving the effectiveness of mother tongue teaching. Tashkent, "Teacher", 1996
5. Nurmonov A. Methodology and methods of linguistic research. Tashkent: Akadem Publishing House, 2010
6. www.natlib.uz
7. www.ziyonet.uz
8. www.kitobxon.com